

Continuity, Discontinuity and Relative Differences in Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 3, 2023

We argue that continuity and discontinuity in special relativity play an important role in the probabilistic wave properties of quantum mechanics. Special relativity is involved with transformations from a rest frame to a frame moving with a constant $-v$, for example. The discontinuity appears in the form of a change from $v=0$ to v , while the continuity arises from Lorentz invariants which indicate one has the same physical state whether it is viewed from a frame with one velocity or another. This invariance applied to E , p (momentum) as a modulus forces a minus sign between the two, in order to allow for linkage with $E=mc^2$ ($c=1$) and $p=0$, i.e. $-E^2 + p^2 = -m^2c^4$ ($c=1$). Another invariant, however, is $A = -Et' + px'$, and in this case the minus sign and the discontinuity lead to a new x', t' (in comparison with the rest frame for a particle with rest mass m_0), but also to $t' \rightarrow t' + b/E$ and $x \rightarrow x' + b/p$ leaving A unchanged ($b = \text{constant}$). The discontinuity in v , which leads to a jump in x', t' (as seen in the moving frame) also manifests itself in a time-length interval which ultimately leads to $\exp(-iEt' + px')$, we argue.

In other words, classically one considers constant velocity as smooth continuous motion, but the introduction of two frames, $v=0$ and $-v$, leads to a discontinuity which leads to “chunkiness” in the form of a frequency and wavelength. If these cannot be perceived classically (as is often the case), then one considers only smoothness.

Relative differences in time or length or in frequency or wavelength, however, can appear in nature for length scales of the order of the frequency/length scale. In the case of n -slit interference-diffraction, a relative difference leads to a “jump” (so to speak) which manifests the wavelength. In particular, a photon moves along the y direction with a phase px (considering a steady state picture). It reaches a two-slit system along the x -axis and there is probability for it to interact with both slits. If one considers two parallel rays from each slit moving towards a point on a screen very far away (as is done traditionally), there is again smooth motion with a rotated p vector (same magnitude), but for a point on the screen to the left of the center, there is a jump in the length associated with the right slit. In other words, there is a jump similar to the $v=0$, $-v$ jump. This leads to a relative difference in length associated with both rays (linked to an OR probability situation using $\exp(ip \cdot r)$). This relative difference in length displays the phase difference initiated by special relativity. In the case of a bound state, different impulse hits by a potential create different momenta which have different phases $\exp(ipx)$ because of special relativity and one has interference.

The same phase $A = -Et + p \cdot r$, which is linked with a chunkiness due to a discontinuity, is also associated with continuity because A is a Lorentz invariant. Thus $A = \text{constant}$ may be used to solve for refraction/reflection problems with or without moving mirrors/interfaces with different indices of refraction. Continuity appears further in a 1-dimensional reflection/refraction problem when applied to the $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x)$ where $E = pc = p_2 c_2$, $p_2 = n_2 p$ and $c_2 = c/n_2$ with $n_1 = 1$, together with a continuity equation for the first derivative.

Thus, both continuity and discontinuity (or jumps), which follow from special relativity, seem to play an important role in quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity

Special relativity considers the comparison of a particle in a rest frame (with rest mass m_0 and $p=0$) to the values E, p as seen from a system moving with $-v$. In one sense, there is continuity or invariance, because one has the same physical entity. In another sense, there is a discontinuity $v=0$ versus $-v$, which one does not consider in Newtonian mechanics. Both the continuity and discontinuity have important physical ramifications.

Continuity leads to the notion of Lorentz invariants, such as:

$$-EE + pp = -m_0m_0 \quad (c=1) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad A = -Et' + p \cdot r' \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) shows that given an $m_0, p=0$, with both m_0 and p increasing when seen from a frame moving at constant $-v$, means a minus sign is needed in the 4-dot product. This is crucial because it leads to a degeneracy in A , i.e. for $p \cdot r' = px'$, one has $t' \rightarrow t' + b/E$ and $x' \rightarrow x' + b/p$ ($b = \text{constant}$) with A unchanged. The discontinuity in $v=0$ and $-v$ means that x', t' differ from x, t in the rest frame because $x'/t' = v$. The discontinuity in $v=0, -v$ leads to the new x', t' , with the Lorentz invariance yielding a minus sign in A . The combination leads to the degeneracy or chunkiness, i.e. a frequency and wavelength if one writes $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, eigenfunctions of translation operators $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-i\partial/\partial x$.

As a result, even though v is smooth, the discontinuity in $v=0, -v$, combined with the continuity of the Lorentz invariance give rise to the frequency-wavelength "chunkiness" of quantum mechanics, we argue.

If one is unable to detect this chunkiness, as in most classical situations, one thinks only of smoothness and continuity. There is a striking case, however, where one does notice discontinuity in quantum, and that is the case of refraction.

Continuity

We argued above that the Lorentz invariance is responsible for continuity. We suggest that this is physically manifested in the case of refraction of a photon. ((1b)) may be used for a photon even though it has no rest mass if one writes:

$$A = |p|t \left(-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t \right) \quad ((2))$$

Here the unit vector points along p and r/t is minus the velocity vector of a moving frame, e.g. a moving mirror (for reflection) or a moving interface (of media with different indices of refraction) for refraction/reflection. The magnitude of momentum as well as the speed of light are discontinuous in different media, but A is constant or continuous. In previous notes, we have used the continuity of ((2)) to find relationships between $|p|$ incident, $|p|$ reflected and $|p|$ refracted (and their angles).

A second example of continuity is that of the probability ($-d/dx$ operator eigenfunction) in a one dimensional refraction problem. Consider a photon moving along the x axis and striking an $n_1=1$ versus n_2 ($n_2 > n_1$) interface along the y axis at $x=0$. Then continuity of probability and d/dx of probability solves for amplitudes, i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2 x) \quad x=0 \quad ((3a))$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = C p^2 \exp(ip^2 x) \quad x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

$$\text{where } E = pc = p^2 c^2 \text{ and } p^2 = n^2 p \text{ and } c^2 = c/n^2 \quad ((4))$$

Thus continuity, i.e. Lorentz invariance, is critical in these problems, but the chunkiness also plays a role because for refraction, one knows a priori that:

$$p(i) = p n(i) \text{ where } n(i) \text{ is the index of refraction and } c(i) = c/n(i) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) represent discontinuities which appear (not due to special relativity), and so A must adjust to these discontinuities in order to remain constant.

Relative Differences

For a single particle or photon, even with a phase $-Et+px$, one still has classical E and p values. If $\exp(ipx)$ is thought of as probability, then the chunkiness of the wavelength seems to require a comparison (OR probability situation) in order to manifest itself.

One example is two-slit interference. A photon moves along the y-axis and reaches a two-slit apparatus (with slits about a wavelength apart) lying along the x-axis. In terms of probability, the photon may interact with both slits and so one has an OR situation with probabilities $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ with $|p|$ remaining unchanged. In order to sense the chunkiness of the wavelength, one needs a "jump" which is out of sync with the wavelength. If the photon receives an impulse hit from one slit or the other and moves towards a point left of center on a screen far away, there is probability for entering the right or left slit. If the right slit, however, is entered, there is a jump in the length traveled with respect to the left slit.. In other words a discontinuity in length is introduced for the right slit in order to shift from vertical motion along the y axis to parallel motion at some angle with respect to the y axis which involves parallel rays from each slit.

This leads to the interference effect being manifested, due to the inherent $A=-Et+ p \cdot r$ degeneracy.. The jump in length of the right ray is like the $v=0, -v$ jump in special relativity. Given that there is already the relativistic chunkiness in phase $p \cdot r$, this jump in length allows the $p \cdot r$ chunkiness to be manifested.

In the case of a bound quantum single particle state, a potential yields impulse hits to the particle. These lead to different momenta represented by $\exp(i p(j) x)$ values and so relative phases automatically exist in an OR situation, but this time due to different p, i.e. different wavelengths. In other words, sudden discontinuities are introduced with each impulse hit, leading to an OR probability situation which manifests the different $\exp(ipx)$ values for a steady stream picture. Even though one has different $p(j)$ values, there is one particle and it is held (localized by) the potential. Thus this particle has a constant energy, except that there is chunkiness in space (humps/troughs) indicating that it has more probability to be in one place than another.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity is associated with Lorentz invariants, i.e. continuity or equivalence, but also discontinuity because one compares E, p, x, t values for two frames moving at a relative velocity of $-v$. Thus there is a discontinuity between $v=0$ and $-v$.

The Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p^2 = -m^2 c^4$ ensures a minus sign in the 4-dot product if E and p both increase from $m_0, p=0$. Given the discrete jump from $v=0$ to v , $x'/t'=v$ and a new set of x', t' is needed in the new frame. This, together with the minus sign, leads to degenerate points for $A = -Et + px$, i.e. $x \rightarrow x + b/p$ and $t \rightarrow t + b/E$. In other words, the discontinuity of $v=0, -v$ ultimately gives rise to a chunkiness represented by a wavelength and frequency if one uses eigenfunctions of translations operators id/dt partial and $-id/dx$ partial. The phase $-Et + p \cdot r$ remains a constant in reflection/refraction problems if r/t is taken to be minus the velocity of a moving mirror or interface. Furthermore, for one dimensional refraction, there is continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative, i.e.. $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$ and the first derivative also at $x=0$.

The chunkiness of the phase $-Et + px$, however, is seen in 2-slit interference. Focusing on $\exp(ipx)$ (as in a steady stream probability scenario), one sees that for a point to the left of the center, the bent right ray travels further than the left. This is because there is a jump from say motion in the y direction to an angled direction (with respect to y). In other words, there is a discontinuity in length between the ray coming from one slit and the other, even if they are both considered to be parallel. This relative difference may be compared with an extra phase $p \cdot r$, which leads to probability augmentation and reduction.

For a bound state, one again has an OR situation with different momenta $\exp(ipx)$ being created by $V(x)$, the potential. In other words, each time an impulse hit occurs, a different p arises and this leads to a discontinuity in the phase of $\exp(ipx)$ (for a steady state problem). A relative phase exists because of the different p values and so when they add, with weights, one also creates a pattern of peaks and troughs. Overall, however, the energy must be constant because one creates a bound system with a fixed energy (like with a free particle), except that the particle has different probabilities to be at different x points. Unlike the free particle, where $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1$, one now has $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We argue that the constant energy E_{bound} follows from special relativity because one considers an overall E with an overall $P = \text{total momentum} = 0$, and this must be associated with $\exp(-i E_{\text{bound}} t)$.